

The state of functional and structural organs of oral cavity in people employed in mining and metallurgical plants

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On the effect of toxic substances in small concentrations on the functional state of the organism, there are two main views. According to a number of authors (1, 2, 3, 4), under the influence of low intensity physical and chemical factors on the body, as a result of training compensatory reactions, a state of non-specific increased resistance is created. Other authors believe that any reaction of the body to the action of a chemical substance cannot be indifferent to it (5, 6). Addiction is only a peculiar form of development of chronic intoxication. Along with this, the problem of the occurrence of dental diseases under the influence of mixtures of harmful chemicals has not been fully studied. The aim of the study was to assess the functional and structural state of organs and tissues of the oral cavity (RP) in workers of the Almalyk mining and metallurgical plant (AMMP group 2) and the Nizhny Gravel metallurgical plant (NGISW 3 group) to justify the planning and development of methods of prevention, treatment, determination of the needs of workers in dental care.

I. Introduction

A total of 1120 people were examined, including 818 workers from 2 industrial enterprises studied (409 people each) and 302 people from the control group (K) (in Tashkent city 1 group), the most numerous age group were people aged 35- 44 years and with experience of 11-15 years - 79.5% of workers. To clarify the nature and extent of the impact of the complex of harmful substances on the organs and tissues of workers' RP, the tooth's sensitivity, pain and discriminatory sensitivity of SOPR, the threshold of taste perception and the functional mobility of the taste of the tongue are determined; microhardness of enamel and dentin, microelement composition of teeth by neutron activation method and comparison with standard samples of IAEA N-4 and NN-1 were determined.

Statistical processing of data obtained in the results of sanitary-hygienic, clinical and functional studies was carried out by the Student method using the application package for IBM PC AT.

II. Main analysis

The results obtained argue that, a sharp decrease in the threshold of excitability of teeth in workers of groups 2 and 3, compared with group 1 ($P < 0.001$); up to 6 times on molars and fangs, 4 times on incisors. Persons with an experience of more than 10 years have a tendency to decrease in sensitivity on molars (54.8 μA), incisors (31.3 μA), fangs (36.6 μA). And the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the vestibular surface of the alveolar ridge in the region of 4, 6 teeth on the palatine side was significantly reduced compared with the 1st group ($P < 0.01$). The discriminatory sensitivity in workers of groups 2 and 3, it was reduced in all areas ($P < 0.01$), in workers of group 2 a decrease in taste sensitivity was found: increase in the threshold of taste for

acidic (in 31.2%) and bitter (in 25 %), lowering the threshold for sweet (in 53.1%) and salty (59.4%).

Changes in the layer-by-layer orientation of the micro hardness of tooth enamel were revealed in workers of the AMMC, since its strength at the surface layer and in the thickness of the enamel differs insignificantly, and the lowest hardness is noted for the dentin-enamel compound. If the micro hardness of various layers of enamel of teeth of the 1st group is taken as 100%, then it was lower for workers at the AMMC: in the surface layer - by 13%, in the thickness of enamel - by 11.8%, in dentin-enamel layer - on the contrary, increased by 1.2.

By studying the microelement composition of enamel, dentin and cement of teeth by neutron activation, 26 workers in the 2nd group, 19 workers in the 3rd group, 31 residents in the 1st group showed that the spectrum of trace elements found in the hard tissues of the teeth of workers is not the same in different enterprises studied ; for example, the Ag content in enamel in workers of groups 2 and 3 was close to the 1-group; in dentin, on the contrary, the workers of groups 2 and 3 did not have Ag groups; the contents of Ag in cement differed even more.

Workers of 2-3 groups are only 1.8 and 4.4 times respectively. The content of Ca + 2 in tooth enamel in groups 2 and 3 was higher than in group. Unlike enamel, in dentin, the Ca + 2 content tended to decrease: in workers 2, in the group by 1.4 times, in workers in the 3rd group, by almost 8 times. The same tendency was observed in determining the Ca + 2 content in tooth cement in both groups of examined workers. The Zn content in the enamel of teeth of groups 2 and 3 of the workers was sharply increased, moreover, in workers of the 2nd group - 17 times versus the 1st group. In dental dentin, the content of Zn in all groups of workers significantly exceeded its k - content (17, 12 times, respectively). An increase in its content (by 4-11 times) was noted in the cement of teeth of workers of groups 2 and 3.

III. Conclusion

The state of functional indicators and nonspecific reactivity of RP tissues in workers is violated, there is a decrease in the threshold of excitability of teeth and paradental tissues, a threshold of pain, gustatory and discriminatory sensitivity, changes in the micro hardness of tooth enamel and dentin, macro and microelement tooth compositions associated with contamination of the working area:

- in the main workshops of the studied productions of AGMK and NTMK, the air of the working area is polluted with a complex of harmful chemicals, including mixtures of substances of hazard classes 1 and 2, depending on the nature of the products, the technology used, the availability and efficiency of the existing sanitary equipment.

- the obtained results are given to us in the scientific justification of the pathogenic mechanisms of the adverse effect of a complex of harmful industrial substances on the soft and hard tissues of RP, creating the opportunity to plan and develop treatment and preventive measures in workers at factories like AMMC and (NGISW taking into account the conditions of the workplace.

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